

SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL FEATURES OF THE USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN HISTORY LESSONS

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Annotation.

This article focuses on socio-pedagogical features of the use of interactive methods in history lessons.

Keywords.

interactive games, interactive methods, history, pedagogical activity, creative thinking, communication, mental attack.

Today, on the basis of reforming the educational system, formation of a competitive environment in the field of state and non-state educational institutions and training, consistent development of the educational system, adaptation of the education and training system to the processes of renewal carried out in society, development of the system of training of personnel, prospects for the social and economic development of, based on the modern achievements of science-culture technology and technology, reconstruction and improvement is carried out in order to create a normative, material-technical and information base that provides for the creative-intellectual and spiritual-moral education of learners, the development of creative skills in them, the development and practical implementation of effective forms and methods of this. Indeed, today many requirements are being put forward to further improve the quality of education, to adapt it to World educational standards, to comprehensively organize the course process. In this, educators are determined as a necessary factor in the formation and direct development of professional and pedagogical skills, knowledge, skills and qualifications. In particular, social science is considered, history in the hours of classes, history teachers should be able to organize classes first of all, scientific, fundamentally interesting at this point.

Interactive methods - a lesson process based on the close cooperation and communication of educators, as well as a way to organize such lessons. The interactive word "Interactive" is derived from the English word interact, meaning

inter – “mutual”, act “Action, influence, activity”. Interactive methods are not only based on active cooperation between the educator and the learner, but also provide close interaction of the learners with each other. In it, a complete understanding of each other is achieved, both educational and educational. With the help of this method, the independent thinking skills of the educated are developed, through which a wide path is opened to their free thinking. This provides an opportunity for the student as well as the student youth to independently make optimal decisions, to think creatively. Interactive methods have a number of goals and objectives. They teach learners to think freely, independently, critically, analytically, logically, and make the right decisions based on them. Forms of use of interactive methods include individualization of training tasks, separation of learners into small groups that can actively and creatively cooperate with each other, stratification of learners in a group according to their intellectual potential, and focusing on the differences between them: creating a free atmosphere of communication and cooperation in the educational process.

It is necessary to become a student in the center of the educational process, and the educational process should be directed, directed at it. The fact that person-oriented education serves as the driving force behind the organization of Educational Labor by the student shows a good result. Because, in this, education gives the teacher and the student the opportunity to constantly seek creative, work on themselves without interruption. The positive course of this situation is a guarantee of quality and effectiveness in education, history the use of interactive methods in the course of the lesson is considered subjective in its essence, that is, each educator should bring the process of education and upbringing to the surface, which is due to his own capabilities, professional skills. The organization of classes using forms and tools is guaranteed by the following interactive methods:

- increase the effectiveness of pedagogical activity;
- determination of interaction between teacher and students;
- ensuring thorough acquisition of knowledge on educational subjects by students;
- formation of independent, free and creative thinking skills in students;
- create the necessary conditions for students to realize their capabilities;
- in the educational process, it is necessary to guarantee the achievement of the primacy of democratic and humanistic ideas.

Various means of using interactive methods in the educational process and their influence, the result of which will soon be manifested by students. They will further increase their interest in science, that is, in history lessons, and will motivate

them to do additional research on themselves. In particular, in students, competencies are formed to work, research and analyze with additional resources on the task. This gives its positive results. Interactive education is an education based on interaction-based interaction, together, in the way of mastering the knowledge, skills, qualifications and certain moral qualities of participants in the educational process. The next criterion for choosing interactive methods is to agree with their educational content, in accordance with its nature. The content of the method is also defined as the part of the movement. For this reason, it is natural that this criterion is taken into account. While using some method serves to reveal the content of the subject more fully, another helps to master it positively.

Another feature of interactive methods to be able to choose and apply thematically is that they are fully compatible with the educational capabilities of students, that is, they are able to ensure the unity of their internal and external conditions for effective educational activities. At this point, it is worth noting that the private capabilities of the educator in the use of interactive teaching methods are also suitable. It is the teaching of the educator with the theory and practice of teaching methods with the laws of the process of knowledge theories are determined taking into account the degree of arming with the theory of the content of education and other existing laws.

Another of the criteria for choosing interactive methods is their compatibility with the forms of Organization of the educational process. Indeed, the gross team-based and individual forms of teaching require different methods. For example, a debate method is considered a debate between two students, while a “mental attack” requires the participation of all students in the group. The reason is that the terms of the method require that. The conformity of interactive methods with pedagogical, technological principles is a generalizing aspect. It is known that pedagogy is designed on the basis of technological as well as certain laws and sheds light on the essence of the basis or subject to the organization of the educational process, and when introduced it serves to ensure the final result, the student's independence to a certain extent. The choice made taking into account the need to solve educational and developmental tasks at the same stage of training, based on the general purpose of education and science, is analyzed and evaluated, and the result is published. An interactive lesson, on the other hand, is such a lesson that students of all classes must be activated. The teacher serves as organizer and supervisor in the process.

The application of interactive methods to the educational process is widespread in the educational system. This in turn assumes the liberalization of the

educational process, democratization, cooperation are also organized in creativity. In a word, it is necessary to be a student at the center of the educational process, and the educational process is required to be focused, oriented towards it. Education aimed at the individual serves as the driving force behind the organization of the Educational Labor of the student, the realization of interest, desire, desires in relation to the science of history. In the process of such education, the cooperation of the teacher and the student is ensured, both of which will have the opportunity to constantly research on themselves. And the positive course of this situation is a guarantee of quality and efficiency in education. In recent times, there has been a lot of use in history lessons for small reports, discussions, work in small groups, debates. When history lessons are organized using interactive methods, students' interest in the history of the world and Uzbekistan increases, becomes more active, skills for working in creativity are formed, students are used to being able to defend their expressed opinions, the skills for collecting, analyzing and processing information. Communication is a style of (communication) interaction. In the process of communication, students exchange ideas, ideas and information. Communication is important in the mental and cultural development of students. Through communication with psychologically advanced individuals, at the expense of extensive opportunities for learning, a person acquires all his higher productive abilities and qualities. In addition, through the use of interactive techniques in history lessons, the opportunity arises for the student to make self-assessment in the educational process. A view of oneself in a critical spirit is formed which prompts their further search. The learning process takes various forms; for example, in the form of singles, pairs, kata and small groups. For the student, the lesson becomes not boring, but the content of an interesting subject being taught. Most importantly, a creative approach to history lessons appears in them. Students can also serve as moderators on their own, rather than just mastering historical science. If all of the factors listed above are the advantages of applying interactive techniques in history lessons, it is also worth noting several of its disadvantages. In particular, the history education process can take a lot of time from the teacher, when very complex materials are studied, it is unlikely that not all students will be able to accurately cope with the issue, or, at the expense of students who find it difficult to control the entire class at the same time, as well as at the expense of students with But, in such conditions, only educators with a highly developed thinking ability, capable of solving problems in their place, observant, with all professional competencies can positively solve the solution to the problem. And in order to achieve such a level, it is necessary for the educator to work on himself and

constantly improve his professional skills. What professional competencies should educators have in order to perfectly organize history lessons? What is professional competence itself? What requirements does it contain? Professional competence is an integrative description and is a set of qualities related to knowledge, skills and competence in educators, ensuring competitiveness in today's market conditions. That is, specialists express professional competence through a system of knowledge, skills, qualifications, methods of activity, psychological characteristics of the individual, characteristics of professional value. Professional competence is evident in the following situations: in complex processes; in the performance of ambiguous tasks; in the use of contradictory information; (for example, in controversial and controversial cases arising from various information given in sources in history lessons) in having an action plan in unforeseen situations; in consistently enriching one's knowledge; in quickly and qualitatively mastering new information; in; and the most important thing is manifested in their re-appropriation and introduction into practice.

Pedagogical scientists usually include the following in the method of interactive teaching: 1) euristic conversation; 2) method of argument; 3) Mental attack; 4) Round Table; 5) method of business Games; 6) selection discussion on practical work and other hands - on interactive teaching methods with a separate teacher. It is worth noting briefly with their content. One method of interactive teaching is euristic conversation, which means Latin – “I gather, I seek”. It is a conversational method with an ancient Greek appearance based on a teaching system known as Socratic conversation. In this way, it is necessary to skillfully draw up questions in history lessons and direct the reader to independently find the right answer to the question posed. The difference between this teaching method and Socrates is that it is lively in a wide range.

To sum up, in the course of the lesson, efforts are being made to use interactive techniques more and more efficiently. Because, through interactive methods, the organization of history lessons in an interactive spirit – becomes a demand for modern education. Modern methods of using interactive methods in history lessons vary, the purpose of applying all of them is to take the qualitative indicator of education to a higher level.

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